

Estudios primarios

ID	Referencia	Fuente
EP-1	Ameri, S., Fard, M. J., Chinnam, R. B., & Reddy, C. K. (2016, October). Survival analysis based framework for early prediction of student dropouts. In Proceedings of the 25th ACM international on conference on information and knowledge management (pp. 903-912).	ACM
EP-2	Chen, Y., Johri, A., & Rangwala, H. (2018, March). Running out of stem: a comparative study across stem majors of college students at-risk of dropping out early. In Proceedings of the 8th international conference on learning analytics and knowledge (pp. 270-279).	ACM
EP-3	Yang, D., Wen, M., Howley, I., Kraut, R., & Rose, C. (2015, March). Exploring the effect of confusion in discussion forums of massive open online courses. In Proceedings of the second (2015) ACM conference on learning@ scale (pp. 121-130).	ACM
EP-4	Zhuhadar, L., Daday, J., Marklin, S., Kessler, B., & Helbig, T. (2019). Using survival analysis to discovering pathways to success in mathematics. Computers in Human Behavior, 92, 487-495.	ACM
EP-5	Gomes, J. B. F., Holanda, M., Koike, C. C., & Costa, M. T. L. (2023, October). Study on computer science undergraduate students dropout at the university of brasilia. In 2023 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE) (pp. 1-7). IEEE.	IEEE
EP-6	Shi, H., & Zhou, Y. (2023, July). Stay or leave? Exploring student factors associated with dropout patterns in massive open online courses. In 2023 IEEE International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies (ICALT) (pp. 26-30). IEEE.	IEEE
EP-7	Pachas, D. A. G., Garcia-Zanabria, G., Cuadros-Vargas, A. J., Camara-Chavez, G., Poco, J., & Gomez-Nieto, E. (2021, October). A comparative study of WHO and WHEN prediction approaches for early identification of university students at dropout risk. In 2021 XLVII Latin American Computing Conference (CLEI) (pp. 1-10). IEEE.	IEEE
EP-8	Csalódi, R., Bagyura, Z., & Abonyi, J. (2021). Mixture of survival analysis models-cluster-weighted Weibull distributions. IEEE Access, 9, 152288-152299.	IEEE
EP-9	Paura, L., & Arhipova, I. (2014). Cause analysis of students' dropout rate in higher education study program. Procedia-social and behavioral sciences, 109, 1282-1286.	Elsevier
EP-10	Costa, F. J. D., Bispo, M. D. S., & Pereira, R. D. C. D. F. (2018). Dropout and retention of undergraduate students in management: a study at a Brazilian Federal University. RAUSP Management Journal, 53(1), 74-85.	Elsevier
EP-11	Barragán, S., González, L., & Calderón, G. (2022). Modelling student dropout risk using survival analysis and analytic hierarchy process for an undergraduate accounting program. Interchange, 53(3), 407-427.	Springer
EP-12	Villano, R., Harrison, S., Lynch, G., & Chen, G. (2018). Linking early alert systems and student retention: a survival analysis approach. Higher Education, 76(5), 903-920.	Springer
EP-13	Ishitani, T. T., & Flood, L. D. (2018). Student transfer-out behavior at four-year institutions. Research in Higher Education, 59(7), 825-846.	Springer
EP-14	Bahi, S., Higgins, D., & Staley, P. (2015). A time hazard analysis of student persistence: A US university undergraduate mathematics major experience. International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education, 13(5), 1139-1160.	Springer
EP-15	Arias Ortiz, E., & Dehon, C. (2013). Roads to success in the Belgian French community's higher education system: Predictors of dropout and degree	Springer

	completion at the Université Libre de Bruxelles. <i>Research in Higher Education</i> , 54(6), 693-723.	
EP-16	Xie, Y. (2023). Childhood Poverty Duration and Its Long-Term Effects on Income and Education in China: A Survival Analysis Based on CHNS Data. <i>Child Indicators Research</i> , 16(6), 2653-2677.	Springer
EP-17	Locke, V. N., & Sparks, P. J. (2019). Who gets held back? An analysis of grade retention using stratified frailty models. <i>Population Research and Policy Review</i> , 38(5), 695-731.	Springer
EP-18	Zeng, Z., & Xie, Y. (2014). The effects of grandparents on children's schooling: Evidence from rural China. <i>Demography</i> , 51(2), 599-617.	Springer
EP-19	Venkatesan, R. G., & Mappillairaju, B. (2024). Early student dropout detection in Indian secondary education with special reference to selected districts in Tamil Nadu: a machine learning-based survival analysis approach. <i>Journal of Computational Social Science</i> , 7(3), 2309-2331.	Springer
EP-20	Chen, C., Sonnert, G., Sadler, P. M., & Malan, D. J. (2020). Computational thinking and assignment resubmission predict persistence in a computer science MOOC. <i>Journal of Computer Assisted Learning</i> , 36(5), 581-594.	Wiley
EP-21	Chen, C., Sonnert, G., Sadler, P. M., Sassellov, D., & Fredericks, C. (2020). The impact of student misconceptions on student persistence in a MOOC. <i>Journal of Research in Science Teaching</i> , 57(6), 879-910.	Wiley
EP-22	Bishop, K. K. (2016). The relationship between retention and college counseling for high-risk students. <i>Journal of College Counseling</i> , 19(3), 205-217.	Wiley
EP-23	Boulaphet, K., & Goto, H. (2020). Determinants of school dropout in Lao People's Democratic Republic: A survival analysis. <i>Journal of International Development</i> , 32(6), 961-975.	Wiley
EP-24	Cardak, B. A., & Vecchi, J. (2016). Graduates, dropouts and slow finishers: The effects of credit constraints on university outcomes. <i>Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics</i> , 78(3), 323-346.	Wiley
EP-25	Dang, B. T. T., & Hoang, T. X. (2024). The impact of compulsory primary education law on the educational attainment of children: Evidence from Vietnam. <i>Asian Economic Journal</i> , 38(1), 118-147.	Wiley
EP-26	Oh, S., Radey, M., Smith, B., & Powers, D. A. (2024). State temporary assistance for needy families policies and high school diploma or equivalent attainment among mothers following a nonmarital birth: An event history analysis. <i>International Journal of Social Welfare</i> , 33(4), 1186-1199.	Wiley
EP-27	Hovdhaugen, E. (2015). Working while studying: The impact of term-time employment on dropout rates. <i>Journal of Education and Work</i> , 28(6), 631-651.	T&F
EP-28	Kim, S., Chang, M., & Park, J. (2018). Survival analysis for Hispanic ELL students' access to postsecondary schools: discrete model or Cox regression?. <i>International Journal of Research & Method in Education</i> , 41(5), 514-535.	T&F
EP-29	Tomlinson, A., Smith, L., Wilcox, C., & Simpson, A. (2024). Academic survival: student retention in sport and exercise sciences. <i>Journal of Further and Higher Education</i> , 48(5), 524-537.	T&F
EP-30	Masci, C., Cannistrà, M., & Mussida, P. (2024). Modelling time-to-dropout via shared frailty Cox models. A trade-off between accurate and early predictions. <i>Studies in Higher Education</i> , 49(4), 763-781.	T&F
EP-31	Caviglia-Harris, J. L. (2022). Community is key: Estimating the impact of living learning communities on college retention and GPA. <i>Education Economics</i> , 30(2), 173-190.	T&F
EP-32	Meggiolaro, S., Giraldo, A., & Clerici, R. (2017). A multilevel competing risks model for analysis of university students' careers in Italy. <i>Studies in Higher Education</i> , 42(7), 1259-1274.	T&F

EP-33	Lamote, C., Speybroeck, S., Van Den Noortgate, W., & Van Damme, J. (2013). Different pathways towards dropout: The role of engagement in early school leaving. <i>Oxford Review of Education</i> , 39(6), 739-760.	T&F
EP-34	Cobre, J., Tortorelli, F. A. C., & de Oliveira, S. C. (2019). Modelling two types of heterogeneity in the analysis of student success. <i>Journal of Applied Statistics</i> , 46(14), 2527-2539.	T&F
EP-35	Zhou, Y., Zhao, J., & Zhang, J. (2023). Prediction of learners' dropout in E-learning based on the unusual behaviors. <i>Interactive Learning Environments</i> , 31(3), 1796-1820.	T&F
EP-36	Buenaño, E., Beletanga, M. J., & Mancheno, M. (2024). What factors are relevant to understanding dropout? Analysis at a co-financed University in Ecuador and Policy Implications, using survival cox models. <i>Journal of Latinos and Education</i> , 23(4), 1400-1415.	T&F